

SOCIAL AND FINANCIAL DISTRESS AMONG CANCER PATIENTS, MINIA, EGYPT

SARA MOHAMMED SAYED

Public Health and Preventive Medicine Department, Faculty of Medicine, Minia University, Egypt.

MAHMOUD ABDEL-FATTAH EL- SHERIEF

Public Health and Preventive Medicine Department, Faculty of Medicine, Minia University, Egypt.

EMAN MOHAMMED MAHFOUZ

Public Health and Preventive Medicine Department, Faculty of Medicine, Minia University, Egypt.

EBTESAM ESMAIL HASSAN

Public Health and Preventive Medicine Department, Faculty of Medicine, Minia University, Egypt.

MARWA GAMAL ABDELREHIM

Public Health and Preventive Medicine Department, Faculty of Medicine, Minia University, Egypt.

Abstract

Background: Cancer is an important relational crisis situation associated with a negative impact on various aspects of a patient's life, including social and financial aspects that affect cancer control programs. **Aim of the study:** To compare some social factors such as marital satisfaction and social support level between cancer patients and controls as well as detect stigmatization and financial distress among cancer cases. **Research methodology:** An observational case-control study was conducted in Minia Oncology Center during one year from 2021 to 2022 to detect the associated social disturbances of cancer. **Results:** Almost half of cases and controls were in the middle age group (30-50 years), the majority of them were married and 55% of cases were diagnosed with cancer for more than one year. Most of employed cancer patients (80.8%) had work disruption mainly in the form of sick leave (41.6%) and more than half of them had financial problems with cancer care. Among married cancer patients, 38.6% were dissatisfied with their relationship compared to 25% of the control group ($P=0.01$). The overall social support score was significantly lower in cases (3.23 ± 1.33) compared to the control group (4.18 ± 1.09). About two-thirds of cancer cases had stigmatization. **Conclusion:** Marital dissatisfaction and low social support were more dominant among cancer cases compared to controls. Cancer stigma and financial distress with cancer care were prevalent among cancer patients and there was a significant inverse relation of stigma with social support as well as marital satisfaction. While there is a positive significant association of social support with marital satisfaction. **Recommendation:** Highlighting the importance of social support and supportive partner relationships as part of cancer support services. Moreover, psychosocial counseling for tailoring stigma-resilience interventions, and developing strategies in governmental and non-governmental organizations for employment and financial support of cancer survivors is important.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a social phenomenon associated with cultural concepts that jeopardize the patients' well-being in addition to being a medical condition that ranks as a leading cause of death (**Stangl et al., 2019**). Social distress is the extent to which social relationships and financial problems are experienced by cancer patients. These negative social and

economic conditions can lead to poorer subjective well-being of patients and affect their quality of life (**Zafar 2016; Da'ar et al., 2023**).

Marital adjustment has been found to be an independent predictive psychosocial factor which refers to the extent to which couples can effectively adapt to changes and challenges in their relationship over time (**Li et al., 2023**). It is associated with better odds of survival and a reduction in psychological distress among various cancer types (**Alyabsi et al., 2021; Jiao et al., 2022**). While struggling with cancer, spouses suffer from living with a cancer patient as they experience burnout during ongoing cancer treatment (**Cihan and Aydogan, 2020**).

There is a general agreement that cancer usually restricts the patient from participating in social activities; this in turn means that cancer patient's opportunities to interact with others and access social support may decrease which can increase stress and negatively impact marital adjustment (**Finck et al., 2018**). Thus, social support has long been considered a protective factor during the cancer trajectory and an essential resource for psychosocial adjustment to this disease (**Bergerot et al., 2022**).

Despite advances and availability of cancer detection and prevention procedures (e.g. screening and vaccination) in the context of making preventive health decisions fear of stigmatization is still being as a potential barrier to health services utilization leading to poor health outcomes (**Badihian et al., 2017**).

Cancer-related social support, marital adjustment and stigma are critical social issues in cancer care via their significant role in managing life crises and health challenges by mitigating cancer-related stress associated with greater well-being and improved quality of life (**Romeo et al., 2019**).

Despite insurance coverage, cancer patients are at higher risk of financial burden for their care compared with individuals without cancer. Some patients report a lack of access to care and nonadherence to therapy with risk for skipping chemotherapy appointments because of higher out-of-pocket costs. Additionally, patients with poor income levels had lower levels of satisfaction in financial aspect (**Chino et al., 2014**). It is increasingly recognized that remaining in work during or after treatment and/or returning to work can be a valued goal for many cancer survivors so, their employment has become an important issue in cancer care (**Butow et al., 2020**).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Population

A case-control study was conducted in Minia Oncology Center and included 400 participants; 200 cancer cases and 200 age and sex-matched healthy controls. The studied cases involved adult clinically stable patients >18 years with a documented diagnosis of cancer of any type from 3 months or more. While healthy individuals free from cancer and age and sex-matched with cases were enrolled as a control group with exclusion of relatives for cases, with a positive family history of any type of cancer. Data

were collected after explaining the nature and aim of the study and obtaining verbal consent from both groups during one year from 2021 to 2022. Patients were asked about financial problems in getting medical care. A standardized validated questionnaire was used to collect data regarding demographic data, disease-specific characteristics, Couples Satisfaction Index, Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support and Stigma Scale for Chronic Illnesses-Short Form.

Couples Satisfaction Index (CSI-16) was applied for married participants and consisted of 16 items to measure marital or relationship satisfaction. To score the CSI-16, sum the responses across all of the items and ranging from 0 to 81. Higher scores indicated higher levels of relationship satisfaction. CSI-16 scores falling below 51.5 suggested notable relationship dissatisfaction (**Funk and Rogge, 2007**).

The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) was designed to measure the individual's subjective assessment of social support adequacy from three specific sources: family, friends and significant others as neighbors **Merhi and Kazarian, (2012)**. This instrument was a 12-item scale with a 7-point Likert format range from 1= very strongly disagree to 7= very strongly agree. The MSPSS was scored by summing individual item scores: -

- Significant Other Subscale: Add items 1, 2, 5, and 10 then divide by 4.
- Family Subscale: Add items 3, 4, 8, and 11 then divide by 4.
- Friends Subscale: Add items 6, 7, 9, and 12 then divide by 4.
- Total Scale: Add all 12 things and then divide them by 12.

If the mean score of the total scale ranging from 1 to 2.9 could be considered low support, a score of 3 to 5 could be considered moderate support and a score from 5.1 to 7 could reflect a higher perception of social support (**Zimet et al., 1988**).

Stigma Scale for Chronic Illnesses-Short Form (SSCI-8) was used to assess experienced stigmatizations as a psychosocial concept. It was derived from a 24-item questionnaire; SSCI-8 was an 8-item newly developed short-form instrument that was appropriate for patients with chronic illnesses (**Molina et al., 2013**).

The items were scored based on a five-point Likert scale from “never” to “always”. This scale represented two forms of enacted and internalized stigma within a unidimensional construct; the sum of the three items “I felt left out of things, I felt embarrassed of my illness, and I felt embarrassed of my physical limitations” were considered to reflect internalized stigma and the other five items of scale reflect enacted stigma. The raw summed score range was 8–40: un-stigmatized: if scale’s score = 8 while stigmatized: if scale’s score ≥ 9 ; Fairly stigmatized if score ≤ 10 or heavily stigmatized if score ≥ 11) (**Daryaafzoon et al., 2020**).

Ethical Consideration

Verbal consent was obtained from all participants after providing comprehensive information about the aim and the nature of the study. The issues of privacy and confidentiality of all study participants had been considered. Ethical permission was taken by the research ethical committee of the Faculty of Medicine at Minia University. Formal acceptance was obtained from the ethical committee and the director of Minia Oncology Center.

Data Statistical Analysis

The collected data were computerized and statistically using the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS), version 20. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to determine the distribution characteristics of continuous variables.

Results were expressed as mean \pm SD and range for continuous variables while frequencies (percentages) for categorical variables.

Comparisons between the means of continuous variables for the two groups were performed using the unpaired Student's t-test for normally distributed variables. Categorical variables were compared by Chi-square or Fisher's exact test "if >20% of cells had expected count less than 5". Pearson's correlation was used for the analysis of correlations for continuous variables. The P value of less than 0.05 was used as a cut-off point for all significant tests and all statistical tests were two-tailed.

RESULTS

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study participants, Minia, Egypt, 2021-2022

Characteristics	Cases (n=200) N (%)	Controls (n=200) N (%)	P value
Age (years)			
<30 years	48 (24%)	28 (14%)	0.240
30-50 years	100 (50%)	122 (61%)	
>50 years	52 (26%)	50 (25%)	
Sex			
Male	86 (43.0%)	95 (47.5%)	0.366
Female	114 (57.0%)	105 (52.5%)	
Residence			
Urban	97 (48.5%)	91 (45.5%)	0.548
Rural	103 (51.5%)	109 (54.5%)	
Marital Status			
Single	18 (9.0%)	16 (8.0 %)	0.601
Married	145 (72.5%)	156 (78.0 %)	
Divorced	29 (14.5%)	21 (10.5 %)	
Widow	8 (4.0%)	7 (3.5 %)	
Education			
Low level	66 (33.0%)	34 (17%)	<0.0001*
High level	134 (67.0 %)	166 (83%)	

*Statistically significant

As shown in Table (1), almost half of the cases and controls were in the middle age group (30-50 years) and the majority of them were married. The education level in cases was significantly lower compared to controls.

Table 2: Disease specific characteristics among the studied cancer patients, Minia Oncology Center, 2021-2022

	Cancer patients (n=200) N (%)
Cancer diagnosis time	
< one year	90 (45%)
≥ one year	110 (55%)
Cancer Stage	
Stage I or II	97 (48.5%)
Stage III or more	103 (51.5%)
Cancer therapy	
Chemotherapy	102 (51%)
Non-chemotherapy	98 (49%)
Cancer type	
Breast	57 (28.5%)
Colon	41 (20.5%)
Others	98 (51%)

Table (2) shows that 28.5% of cases have breast cancer, 55% of them are diagnosed with cancer for more than one year and more than half of cases received chemotherapy.

Table 3: Financial distress among the studied cancer patients, Minia Oncology Center, 2021-2022

	Cancer cases (n=200) N (%)	
Occupation status		
Un employed	75 (37.5%)	
Employed		125 (62.5%)
Work disruption		(n=125)
No		24 (19.2%)
Yes	101 (80.8%)	
Lost job	28 (22.4%)	
Sick leave	52 (41.6%)	
Part-time	24 (19.2%)	
Changes work schedules/ place		21 (16.8%)
I can get medical care without financial troubles		
Yes	38 (19%)	
Uncertain	43 (21.5%)	
No	119 (59.5%)	
I can afford for cancer care		
Yes	52 (26%)	

Uncertain	No	37 (18.5%)	111 (55.5%)
-----------	----	------------	-------------

Table (3) showed that more than one-third of cancer patients were unemployed. Moreover, the majority of employed patients had disruption in their work (80.8%), mostly in the form of sick leave (41.6%) and lost job (22.4%). More than half of cancer patients had financial troubles in getting medical care and 55.5% of them couldn't afford cancer care.

Table 4: Stigma characteristics among the studied cancer cases according to Stigma Scale for Chronic Illnesses 8-Item, Minia Oncology Center, 2021-2022

Stigma characteristics	Cancer cases (n=200)
	Mean ± SD Range
Overall stigma score	9.86 ± 1.96 (8 – 16)
Forms of stigma	
Internalized stigma	4.47 ± 1.57 (3 -9)
Enacted stigma	5.40 ± 0.66 (5 -7)
Stigmatization	N (%)
Un stigmatized	62 (31.0%)
Stigmatized	138 (69.0%)
Grades of stigma (n=138)	N (%)
Fairly	91 (65.9%)
Heavily	47 (34.1%)

The overall mean stigma score was 9.86 ± 1.96 among the cancer patients with the mean score of internalized stigma was 4.47 ± 1.57 while the mean score of enacted stigma was 5.40 ± 0.66 . In conclusion, 69.0% of cancer patients were stigmatized with majority of them of fair degree.

Table 5: Comparison of social variables between the studied groups, Minia, Egypt, 2021-2022

	Cases (n=200) Mean ± SD Range	Controls (n=200) Mean ± SD Range	P value
Couple Satisfaction score**	(n=145) 48.03 ± 12.78 23 – 65	(n=156) 51.69 ± 11.16 25 -71	0.008*
Marital satisfaction degree	N (%)	N (%)	
Dissatisfaction	56 (38.6%)	39 (25.0%)	0.011*
Satisfaction	89 (61.4 %)	117 (75.0%)	
Overall Social support score	3.23 ± 1.33 (2.42 – 5.83)	4.18 ± 1.09 (2.42– 5.33)	<0.0001*
Classification of social support	N (%)	N (%)	
Low support	80 (40.0%)	49 (24.5%)	

Moderate Support	98 (49.0%)	67 (33.5%)	<0.0001*
High Support	22 (11.0%)	84 (42.0%)	
Forms of social support			
Significant other subscale	2.91 ± 1.65	3.38 ± 1.31	0.003*
Family subscale	4.46 ± 1.67	5.07 ± 1.52	<0.0001*
Friend subscale	3.22 ± 1.33	4.08 ± 1.50	<0.0001*

*Statistically significant.
satisfaction.

** Higher scores indicate higher levels of relationship

Table (5) showed that the overall couple satisfaction and social support scores were significantly lower in cases (48.03±12.78) and (3.23 ± 1.33) compared to control group (51.69 ± 11.16) and (4.18 ± 1.09) respectively. As regard grading of marital satisfaction and social support scales, 38.6% of cases were significantly dissatisfied in their relationship compared to 25% of control group (p value 0.01) while 11% of cases received high support compared to 42% of control with observed significant difference (p value<0.0001). Family support with mean 4.46 ± 1.67 was the most common social support forms among cases followed by friend support (3.22 ± 1.33) which significantly lower compared to control group (p value < 0.0001).

Table 6: Social Support and Marital Satisfaction as regards the Participants' Characteristics Minia, Egypt, 2021-2022

Participant characteristics	Social support score Mean ± SD		Couple satisfaction score Mean ± SD	
	Cases (n=200)	Controls (n=200)	Cases (n=145)	Controls (n=156)
Age (years)				
<30 years	2.78 ± 0.58	3.35 ± 0.84	32.27 ± 10.95	38.71 ± 9.78
30-50 years	3.37 ± 0.98	4.19 ± 1.09	46.08 ± 11.75	50.38 ± 9.02
>50 years	3.78 ± 0.88	4.61 ± 0.96	57.20 ± 7.41	61.07 ± 7.82
P value	<0.0001*	<0.0001*	<0.0001*	<0.0001*
Sex				
Male	3.73 ± 0.83	4.21 ± 1.07	51.19 ± 10.16	52.21 ± 9.05
Female	3.38 ± 1.0	4.14 ± 1.11	44.99 ± 14.29	51.26 ± 12.69
P value	0.011*	0.655	0.003*	0.597
Marital Status				
Unmarried	3.06 ± 0.88	4.14 ± 1.10		
Married	3.71 ± 0.95	4.18 ± 1.09	-----	-----
P value	<0.0001*	0.821		
Education level				
Low level	3.35 ± 0.99	3.98 ± 1.03	46.30 ± 12.68	46.79 ± 12.06
High level	3.62 ± 0.96	4.21 ± 1.10	52.55 ± 12.07	52.77 ± 10.05
P value	0.061	0.267	0.008*	0.010*
Occupation				
Un employed	3.44 ± 0.94	4.05 ± 1.14	48.59 ± 14.43	51.33 ± 14.09
Employed	3.58 ± 0.99	4.24 ± 1.07	47.71 ± 11.84	51.88 ± 9.31
P value	0.304	0.264	0.690	0.771
Work disruption	(n=125)	(n=134)	(n=93)	(n=102)

No	3.92 ± 1.07	4.27 ± 1.02	54.00 ± 9.28	52.45 ± 8.96
Yes	3.51 ± 0.96	4.13 ± 1.19	45.76 ± 11.92	50.12 ± 10.33
P value	0.068	0.492	0.004*	0.278
Cancer diagnosis time				
< one year	3.24 ± 0.91		39.97 ± 11.72	
≥ one year	3.77 ± 0.96	----	52.13 ± 11.30	-----
P value	<0.0001*		<0.0001*	
Cancer Stage				
Stage I or II	3.32 ± 0.95		41.49 ± 12.72	
Stage III or more	3.73 ± 0.96	-----	52.26 ± 10.95	-----
P value	0.002*		<0.0001*	
Cancer therapy				
Chemotherapy	3.41 ± 0.90		42.63 ± 12.24	
Non-chemotherapy	3.65 ± 1.03	-----	52.41 ± 11.53	-----
P value	0.094		<0.0001*	

Table (6) showed that social support and marital satisfaction scores were significantly low in young, females, unmarried and those of cancer diagnosis less than one year with early cancer stage. Additionally, marital satisfaction was significantly low among employed cases with work disruption and those received chemotherapy. On the other hand, significantly higher marital satisfaction score for cases and controls of high education level.

Table 7: Correlation analysis for scores of the study scales among cancer patient, Minia Oncology Center, 2021-2022

Variables	R	P value
Couple Satisfaction score Social support score	0.56	<0.0001*
Couple Satisfaction score stigma score	-0.59	<0.0001*
Social support score stigma score	-0.41	<0.0001*

*Statistically significant.

This table showed that there is an inverse relationship between stigma with social support as well as marital satisfaction while a positive significant association between marital satisfaction with social support exists.

DISCUSSION

The current study was a case-control conducted in Minia Oncology Center, Minia, Egypt to compare social factors between cancer cases and healthy controls as well as detect stigmatization and financial distress among cancer cases. In the present study, more than half of the cases and controls were females and of middle age (**Table 1**). These findings were approximate to a study of marital adjustment among 130 cancer patients at the oncology division of the Jaen university hospital in Spain which reported that half of cases

were females (**Ruiz-Marin et al., 2021**). In addition to another study done on 88 patients attended surgery centers at the oncology department of the university hospital of Palermo reported that a mean age of cases was 48.66 ± 9.86 (**Luca et al., 2017**).

Regarding the clinical data findings in this study, 55% of patients were diagnosed with cancer for more than one year (**Table 2**) while 34.6% were diagnosed with cancer for more than one year in a previous study done on 130 cancer patients (**Ruiz-Marin et al., 2021**) in addition to 51.5% of current cases at stage III or more which nearly similar to study was done on 280 cancer patients to assess the level of patient satisfaction and its association psychosocial variables in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, reported that 48% at stage III or IV (**Alosaimi et al., 2022**).

In the current study as regard financial problems among cancer patients, the majority of employed patients had disruption in their work (80.8%), mostly in form of sick leave (41.6%) (**Table 3**). These were approximating with a previous study reported that 37.8% of cancer cases were on sick leave (**Ruiz-Marin et al., 2021**) and another study done on 119 patients undergoing outpatient chemotherapy reported that 27.7% were employed but had a sick leave of more than 3 months which was lower than this study findings (**Hervàs et al., 2020**). Additionally, more than half of cancer patients had financial troubles in getting medical care and 55.5% of them cannot afford cancer care (**Table 3**). These studied findings were in accordance with a previous study among 174 cancer patients reported that 46.6% of them had significant financial burden while 50.0% of them reported moderate to minor financial burden (**Chino et al., 2014**). These findings could be explained by high cost of cancer treatment, even with insurance coverage in addition to job disruption related to cancer and low socioeconomic status among these patients leading to financial stress.

This study revealed that the overall mean stigma score was 9.86 ± 1.96 while the means of internalized and enacted stigma were 4.47 ± 1.57 and 5.40 ± 0.66 respectively (**Table 4**). Nearly higher results were found in a cross-sectional study included 223 breast cancer patients in Iran reported that the mean of total stigma score was 11.75 ± 5.56 according to the SSCI-8 scale while mean scores for enacted and internalized stigma were 6.99 ± 3.44 and 4.77 ± 2.63 respectively (**Zamanian et al., 2022**).

The present study observed that 69.0% of cancer patients were being stigmatized (**Table 4**). This was in line with the higher percentage of stigmatized patients (79%) among 200 advanced breast and colon cancers (**Pham et al., 2021**) while these findings were opposite to a national survey in Korea where 30% of survivors reported a feeling of stigma (**Cho et al., 2013**). This could be explained by more than half of the studied patients were females and were in middle age who were exposed to societal pressure to conform to certain norms of health and appearance that can lead to stigmatization. Moreover, limited access to counseling for cancer patients and their families that can exacerbate the feelings of stigma in addition to limited healthcare facilities, well-trained medical staff which can result in suboptimal care for cancer patients leading to misconceptions and stigmatization.

In the current study, 38.6% of married cancer patients were more dissatisfied in their relationship with their partner compared to 25% of controls (**Table 5**). This could be justified by struggling with cancer, spouses begin suffering as they experience burnout during ongoing cancer treatment (**Cihan and Aydogan, 2020**) in addition to 40% of cases in this study received low social support (**Table 5**). Similar results were found in a study at the oncology center in Spain concluded that 44.3% of participants had problems with their marital life due to illness (**Shiri et al., 2018**). In contrast to previous findings, 15% were classified as experiencing poor marital adjustment among 130 cancer patients (**Ruiz-Marin et al., 2021**).

This study found that the total mean score of social support among cases was 3.23 ± 1.33 while the sub-dimensions of the social support scale were 4.46 ± 1.67 , 3.22 ± 1.33 and 2.91 ± 1.65 for family, friends and significant others sub-dimensions support respectively while these social support findings were higher among control groups regarding total mean score (4.18 ± 1.09) and for family (5.07 ± 1.52), friends (4.08 ± 1.50) and significant others (3.38 ± 1.31) (**Table 5**). This could be explained by cancer usually restricts the patient from participating in social activities and decreases opportunities for interacting with others and accessing social support.

These social support findings were different from a cross-sectional study included 428 breast cancer patients in seven health facilities in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia using the same social support scale showed that participants' total scores of social support were found to be high 5.86 ± 1.40 and the sub-dimensions of the social support scale showed 6.38 ± 1.24 , 3.97 ± 2.36 and 6.00 ± 1.71 for family, friends and significant others sub-dimensions respectively (**Wondimagegnehu et al., 2019**). Another study conducted on 196 breast cancer patients who were on systemic treatment or follow-up care found that total social support score was found to be very high 6.08 ± 1.14 and the means sub-dimensions scales were 6.25 ± 1.11 , 5.50 ± 1.59 and 6.25 ± 1.39 for family, friends and significant others respectively (**Teshome et al., 2021**). This could be justified by the higher cancer stigma from community culture which leads to lower social interaction and support in the present study compared to these previous studies.

Regarding forms of social support among cases, the most support form was family followed by friend (**Table 5**). A systematic review study also found the same results as emotional support by spouses, family members then friends were the main forms of support for women with breast cancer (**Fernandes et al., 2014**). This could be attributed to the emotional bond and trust as a result of their close relationships making family members and friends are the first choices for seeking support during challenging times. Additionally, many patients prefer to share their experiences and vulnerabilities with those comfortable providing a sense of security when dealing with the uncertainties of cancer.

The present study showed that social support and marital satisfaction scores were significantly low in young, females, unmarried and those of cancer diagnosis less than one year with early cancer stage. Additionally, marital satisfaction was significantly low among employed cases experiencing work disruption and those received chemotherapy.

On the other hand, significantly higher marital satisfaction score for cases and controls of high education level (**Table 6**).

These findings were corresponding to evidence shows that females, younger patients, and patients receiving chemotherapy were more vulnerable to inadequate support and partner's relationship satisfaction (**Enns et al., 2013**). This could be justified by young, and female's patients experience stigma that discourage them from seeking social support in addition to younger individuals might be more concerned about fertility preservation, but cancer treatments could affect fertility leading to additional distress and concerns within the marriage while patients receiving chemotherapy could experience side effects that impact their physical and emotional well-being.

Another study revealed the same results as social distress was significantly higher in patients diagnosed within one year than in patients diagnosed more than one year prior and at early cancer stage (**Da'ar et al., 2023**). This attributed to the shock of the diagnosis lead to difficult to engage socially or seek support actively and this emotional shock making it challenging for both partners to adapt to the new reality, thus higher levels of distress and lower marital satisfaction.

An inverse relation of marital satisfaction with work disruption could be explained by cancer diagnosis and treatment that leads to significant medical expenses, even with insurance coverage led to financial stress in addition to work disruption among cancer survivors can strain marital satisfaction through reduce income especially if the couple had relied on dual incomes. On the other hand, as regard a positive relation of marital satisfaction with education level in this study, another cross-sectional study to evaluate marital adjustment among 130 cancer patients in Spain which reported approximate findings concluded a good marital adjustment within high education level cancer patients (**Ruiz-Marin et al., 2021**). This could be justified by the couples with higher levels of education often having well-developed communication skills which is essential for discussing the challenges associated with a cancer diagnosis led to a stronger sense of understanding and closeness, contributing to higher marital satisfaction.

This study revealed a negative association of stigma with social support and marital satisfaction while positive association of marital satisfaction with social support (**Table 7**). These findings were consistent with previous literature explaining that cultural beliefs and community expectations could affect negative attitudes toward cancer such as "cancer being contagious" leading to avoidance of close physical contact with cancer patients after their cancer diagnosis, thus closely associated with reduced social relationships and dissatisfaction with their partner (**Badihian et al., 2017**). Additionally, stigma led to self-isolation from the community to keep secret cancer to avoid negative experiences resulting in a lack of social support (**Stergiou-Kita et al., 2016**).

On the other side, several subgroups were more likely to have unmet social support needs among cancer patients including those who were not married, had lower household income, had higher symptom burden and older adults (**Williams et al., 2019**). Another

Study among adults with cancer showed that patients at high risk for low social support included those who are unmarried in addition to having poor psychological well-being, chronic diseases and metastatic disease (**Thompson et al., 2017**). This could be attributed to lacking a close partner could result in a reduced availability of emotional support through providing a source of comfort, reassurance, and a listening in addition to practical support for daily tasks while marital satisfaction often associated with effective communication and openness between partners so, more likely to express their needs, listen to each other, and provide emotional support during their illness.

CONCLUSION

Marital satisfaction and received social support were lower among cancer cases compared to the control group with observed significant differences. The most common social support forms are family support followed by friend support for cases and controls. Additionally, the majority of employed cancer patients had disruption in their work and more than half of them had financial troubles in getting medical care. More than two-third of stigmatized cases were of fair degree.

References

- 1) **Stangl A L, Earnshaw V A, Logie C H, van Brakel W, Simbayi L C, Barré I, Dovidio J F (2019):** The Health Stigma and Discrimination Framework: a global, crosscutting framework to inform research, intervention development, and policy on health-related stigmas. *BMC Med.*;17(1):1–3.
- 2) Li J, Liu L, Chen M, Su W, Yao T and Li X (2023): Effect of intimacy and dyadic coping on psychological distress in pancreatic cancer patients and spousal caregivers. *Frontiers in Psychology*; 14: 1040460.
- 3) **Alyabsi M, Ramadan M, Algarni M, Alshammari K and Jazieh AR (2021):** The effect of marital status on stage at diagnosis and survival in Saudis diagnosed with colorectal cancer: cancer registry analysis. *Sci Rep.*;11(1):8603. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-88042-9
- 4) **Jiao D, Ma Y, Zhu J, Dai H, Yang Y, Zhao Y, Guo X and Liu Z (2022):** Impact of Marital Status on Prognosis of Patients with Invasive Breast Cancer: A Population-Based Study Using SEER Database. *Front. Oncol.*; 12:913929. doi: 10.3389/fonc.2022.913929
- 5) **Cihan H and Aydogan D (2020):** Relational resilience as a protective factor in marital adjustment of couples with cancer: a dyadic model. *Dusunen Adam The Journal of Psychiatry and Neurological Sciences*; 33:281-288.
- 6) **Finck C, Barradas S, Zenger M and Hinz A (2018):** Quality of life in breast cancer patients: associations with optimism and social support. *Int J Clin Health Psychol*; 18:27–34.
- 7) **Bergerot C D, Costas-Muñiz R, Lee D and Philip E J (2022):** Social Support as a Protective Factor for Patients with Cancer during the Pandemic, *Cancer Investigation*; 40 (6): 473-474. DOI: 10.1080/07357907.2022.2074410
- 8) **Badihian S, Choi E, Kim I, Parnia A, Manouchehri N, Badihian N, Tanha J M, Guallar E and Choc j (2017):** Attitudes Toward Cancer and Cancer Patients in an Urban Iranian Population. *The Oncologist*; 22:944–950.
- 9) **Romeo A, Di Tella M, Ghiggia A, Tesio V, Gasparetto E, Stanizzo MR, Torta R and Castelli L (2019):** The traumatic experience of breast cancer: which factors can relate to the post-traumatic outcomes? *Front Psychol.*; 10:891.
- 10) **Funk J L and Rogge RD (2007):** Testing the Ruler with Item Response Theory: Increasing Precision of Measurement for Relationship Satisfaction with the Couples Satisfaction Index. *Journal of Family*

- Psychology; 21: 572-583. **Funk J L and Rogge RD (2007)**: Testing the Ruler with Item Response Theory: Increasing Precision of Measurement for Relationship Satisfaction with the Couples Satisfaction Index. *Journal of Family Psychology*; 21: 572-583.
- 11) **Merhi R and Kazarian S (2012)**: Validation of the Arabic Translation of Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (Arabic-MSPSS) in a Lebanese Community Sample. *The Arab Journal of Psychiatry*; 23 (2): 159 -168.
 - 12) **Zimet GD, Dahlem NW, Zimet SG and Farley GK (1988)**: The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support. *Journal of Personality Assessment*; 52: 30-41
 - 13) **Molina Y, Choi S W, Cella D and Rao D (2013)**: The stigma scale for chronic illnesses 8-Item version (SSCI-8): Development, validation and use across neurological conditions. *Int J Behav Med*; 20 (3): 450-460. doi:10.1007/s12529-012-9243-4.
 - 14) **Daryaafzoon M, Amini-Tehrani M, Zohrevandi Z, Hamzehlouiyani M, Ghotbi A, Zarrabi-Ajami S and Zamanian H (2020)**: Translation and Factor Analysis of the Stigma Scale for Chronic Illnesses 8-Item Version among Iranian Women with Breast Cancer; *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*; 21 (2): 449-455.
 - 15) **Ruiz-Marin C M, Molina-Barea R, Slim M and Calandre E P (2021)**: Marital Adjustment in Patients with Cancer: Association with Psychological Distress, Quality of Life, and Sleep Problems. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*;18: 7089. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18137089>
 - 16) **Hervàs A, Montraveta R, Corral S, Pintado L, Baeza T, Arnau A and Vall A (2021)**: Factors contributing to satisfaction with care in cancer outpatients. *Supportive Care in Cancer*; 29: 4575–4586.
 - 17) **Alosaimi F D, Alsaleh F S, Alsughayer LY, Altamimi LA, Alfurayh I A, Abdel-Aziz N M and Alsaleh KA (2022)**: Psychosocial and clinical predictors of patient satisfaction with cancer care. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*; 30(4): 414-420.
 - 18) **Shiri F H, Mohtashami J, Nasiri M, Manoochehri H and Rohani C (2018)**: Stigma and related factors in Iranian people with cancer. *Asian Pacific journal of cancer prevention. Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*;19 (8): 2285-2290
 - 19) **Wondimagegnehu A, Abebe W, Abraha A and Teferra S (2019)**: Depression and social support among breast cancer patients in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *BMC cancer*; 19: 836-844.
 - 20) **Teshome B, Trabitzsch J, Afework T, Addissie A, Kaba M, Kantelhardt E J and Getachew S (2021)**: Perceived barriers to timely treatment initiation and social support status among women with breast cancer in Ethiopia. *Plos one*; 16(9): e0257163.
 - 21) **Fernandes A F, Cruz A, Moreira C, Santos M C and Silva T (2014)**: Social support provided to women undergoing breast cancer treatment: A study review. *Advances in Breast Cancer Research*; 3(2): 47-53.
 - 22) **Zamanian H, Amini-Tehrani M, Jalali Z, Daryaafzoon M, Ramezani F, Malek N, Adabimohazab M, Hozouri R and Rafiei Taghanaky F (2022)**: Stigma and Quality of Life in Women with Breast Cancer: Mediation and Moderation Model of Social Support, Sense of Coherence, and Coping Strategies. *Front. Psychol.* 13:657992. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.657992
 - 23) **Pham N T, Lee J J, Pham N H, Phan T D Q, Tran K, Dang H B, Teo I, Malhotra C, Finkelstein E A and Ozdemir S (2021)**: The prevalence of perceived stigma and self-blame and their associations with depression, emotional well-being and social well-being among advanced cancer patients: evidence from the APPROACH cross-sectional study in Vietnam. *BMC Palliat Care*; 20:104-113.
 - 24) **Cho J, Smith K, Choi E K, Kim I R, Chang Y J, Park HY, Guallar E and Shim YM (2013)**: Public attitudes toward cancer and cancer patients: a national survey in Korea. *Psycho-Oncology*; 22(3): 605-613.

- 25) **Badihian S, Choi E, Kim I, Parnia A, Manouchehri N, Badihian N, Tanha J M, Guallar E and Choc j (2017):** Attitudes Toward Cancer and Cancer Patients in an Urban Iranian Population. *The Oncologist*; 22:944–950.
- 26) **Stergiou-Kita M, Pritlove C, Kirsh B (2016):** The “Big C” -stigma, cancer, and workplace discrimination. *J Cancer Surviv*; 10:1035-1050.
- 27) **Williams G R, Pisu M, Rocque G B, Williams C P, Taylor R A, Kvale E A, Partridge E E, Bhatia S and Kenzik K M (2019):** Unmet social support needs among older adults with cancer. *Cancer*; 125(3): 321-483.
- 28) **Thompson T, Pérez M, Kreuter M, Margenthaler J, Colditz G and Jeffe D B (2017):** Perceived Social Support in African American Breast Cancer Patients: Predictors and Effects. *Social Science & Medicine*; 192:134–142.
- 29) **Chino F, Peppercorn J, Taylor D H Lu Y, Samsa G, Abernethy A B and Zafar y (2014):** Self-Reported Financial Burden and Satisfaction with Care Among Patients with Cancer. *The Oncologist*; 19:414–420.
- 30) **Da'ar OB, Jradi H, Alkaiyat M, Alolayan A and Jazieh A R (2023):** Social Distress among Cancer Patients: Differential Effects of Risk Factors and Attenuating Role of Culturally Specific Social Support. In *Healthcare*; 11 (13): 1876.
- 31) **Zafar Y S (2016):** Financial toxicity of cancer care: It's time to intervene. *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.* 108, djv370.
- 32) **Enns A, Waller A, Groff S L, Bultz B D, Fung T, Carlson LE (2013):** Risk Factors for Continuous Distress Over a 12-Month Period in Newly Diagnosed Cancer Outpatients. *J. Psychosoc. Oncol.*; 31: 489–506.
- 33) **Butow P, Laidsaar-Powell R and Konings S (2020):** Return to work after a cancer diagnosis: a meta-review of reviews and a meta-synthesis of recent qualitative studies. *J Cancer Surviv*; 14:114–134.
- 34) **Luca R D, Dorangricchia P, Salerno L, Coco G L and Cicero G (2017):** The Role of Couples' Attachment Styles in Patients' Adjustment to Cancer. *Oncology*; 92:325–334.